

30 July - 4 August

BELFAST

23rd International Conference on Composite Materials

High Temperature Mechanical Properties of Carbon/Phenolic Composite at High Heating Rate

X. Lin^{1*}, W. Xie¹

¹ National Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on Advanced Composites in Special Environments, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, China

Background

Cross Section of Carbon/Phenolic Specimen under CT Scanning

Virgin ablator → Charring ablator + Pyrolysis gases

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy of the Specimen

- As a heat resistant material, **carbon/phenolic composite** has excellent high-temperature mechanical properties, making it **widely used in aerospace engineering**.
- At high temperatures, materials will undergo pyrolysis and ablation, forming a **composite structure** of the virgin layer, pyrolysis layer, and char layer, while also affecting their high-temperature mechanical properties.
- Adding **modified phases** to the composite matrix can improve its ablation resistance and mechanical properties.

Pyrolysis and ablation at high temperatures

Thermogravimetric (TG) Curves of Phenolic Matrix Composites at Different Heating Rates^[1]

TG and DTG Curves of Carbon/Phenolic Composite

The basis for controlling the degree of material pyrolysis through high-temperature mechanical testing. *DTG: Abbreviation of derivative thermogravimetric analysis

The Weight Loss Rate of Materials at High Heating Rates and Different Temperatures^[2]

XRD and Raman Spectra of the Composite at Different Temperatures

- The higher the temperature and the longer the pyrolysis time, the higher the graphitization degree of phenolic matrix, and the lower the disorder degree and fewer defects.

*XRD: Abbreviation of X-Ray diffraction

Mechanical properties

Split-Type Radiation Heating High Temperature Mechanical Testing Machine and its Compression Device

- The specimen is first placed at room temperature chamber, and when the high-temperature chamber reaches the testing temperature, it is lifted into the testing area and the holding time is accurately controlled to obtain the high-temperature mechanical properties of carbon/phenolic composite at different pyrolysis degrees.

Stress-Displacement Curves and In-plane Compressive Strength of Carbonized Carbon/Phenolic Composite at Different Temperatures

Typical Morphology of Specimen under Optical Microscope (OM) and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) after High Temperature Mechanical Test

High Temperature Mechanical Test Parameters and In-plane Compressive Strength of Carbon/Phenolic Composite

Test temperature(°C)	200	400	600	800	1000	1200	1400	1600	1800
Holding time(minutes)	10	37	25	81	115	83	82	71	66
Weight loss rate(%)	1.81	15.92	17.71	19.12	20.75	22.37	23.71	24.05	24.20
In-plane compressive strength(MPa)	76.91	26.64	23.42	48.24	52.38	56.42	57.79	59.04	60.16

Degree of pyrolysis:

$$\alpha = \frac{W_1}{W_0}$$

W_1 — the weight-loss rate of the specimen during the test (%)
 W_0 — end point of the pyrolytic reaction at different temperatures (25.5%)
 S — high-temperature in-plane compression strength
 α — degree of pyrolysis ($0 < \alpha \leq 1$)
 T — 1% of the test temperature (°C, $4 \leq T \leq 18$)

High temperature compressive strength fitting based on material pyrolysis degrees and testing temperatures:

$$S = 0.8055T^2 + 9514\alpha^2 - 336.6\alpha T + 294.4T - 13200\alpha + 4208.16$$

A Comparison of the Test Value and the Fitting Curve

Accurate

References

[1] F. Torres-Herrador, J. B. E. Meurisse, F. Panerai, et al. A high heating rate pyrolysis model for the phenolic impregnated carbon ablator (PICA) based on mass spectroscopy experiments[J]. Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis, Vol. 141, No. 104625, pp 1-10, 2019.

[2] X. Lin, F. Yi, W. Xie, et al. Experimental research on the high-temperature compression mechanical properties of carbon/phenolic composites in rapid carbonization conditions[J]. Polymer Composites, Vol. 44, No. 5, pp 3007-3019, 2023.